

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE X

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

October 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
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World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue X (October 2025), pp.153-162, International
ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X
Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com
Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services
DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183
National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The Digital Classroom Unveiled: An Analysis of the Effect of Online Learning on the Academic Achievement of BSED Students in a Local Community College

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ABSTRACT

This study, titled "*The Effect of Online Learning on the Academic Achievement of BSED Students in Local Community College*," aimed to explore how students perceive online learning and its impact on their academic performance. Using descriptive and correlational methods, the research gathered insights from 30 BSED students across different age groups, sexes, and year levels. Results revealed that while students generally have access to reliable technology and demonstrate strong time management skills, their academic performance, engagement, and motivation in online learning remain moderately affected. Challenges such as technical issues, poor concentration, and feelings of isolation were found to significantly hinder learning effectiveness.

Furthermore, statistical analysis showed a high positive correlation between age and year level with the perceived effect of online learning, indicating that older and more academically experienced students tend to adapt better. Gender, however, showed no significant influence. These findings suggest the need for targeted interventions that address both technological barriers and emotional engagement to enhance the online learning experience and academic success of students.

Keywords: *Online Learning, Academic Achievement, BSED Students, Engagement, Time Management, Access to Technology, Challenges, Correlation Analysis, Abuyog Community College.*

INTRODUCTION

Online learning, also referred to as e-learning or virtual instruction, was used to deliver academic content through digital platforms and internet-based technologies that use digital resources for communication, lesson delivery, assessment outside conventional classrooms. Students and teachers connect through virtual environments to work together, exchange educational materials, participate in discussions and finish their tasks. According to Dhawan (2020), online learning offered flexible learning options which make education accessible to students who want to study at any time from any location.

Recent studies also indicated that students in online and blended learning environments had achieved comparable or even superior academic outcomes compared to traditional classroom settings (Garrison & Vaughan, 2018).

Online learning provided many benefits to students but it created specific difficulties for them to overcome. The combination of inadequate internet access, insufficient technology resources, and decreased student participation led to negative learning outcomes, according to Adedoyin and

Soykan (2020). The study of Aguilera-Hermida (2020) demonstrated that students faced difficulties with maintaining motivation and self-regulation and staying focused when learning in virtual environments.

In the Philippines, the rapid transition from classroom learning to digital education brought both positive aspects and negative consequences for Filipino students in their educational journey. The study of Alvarez (2020) demonstrated that online learning enhanced student digital skills but simultaneously caused students to lose focus and motivation and reduced their social interaction.

On the other hand, Tang et al. (2021) demonstrated that students' academic results depend on their readiness for online learning and digital competence but these factors differ between college students based on their access to technology and their motivation levels and learning environment. The evolution of online learning has established difficulties for students to succeed academically through digital platforms. This study examined how online learning affected BSED students at Abuyog Community College (ACC) through academic performance assessment to address the gaps about online learning effects on student achievement and learning results. The research focused on academic achievement assessment of BSED students through online learning because previous studies mostly examined perceptions and satisfaction and readiness levels.

This study on BSED students' academic achievement through online learning helped teachers understand which digital education elements—technology access and student engagement and self-regulation—most impact student success. The research findings showed possible ways to boost academic results and create better learning experiences through online education improvements.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study was to investigate if online learning had an effect on academic achievement of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students. Specifically, the purpose of this research study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the profile of BSED students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Year Level
2. What is the level of the effect of online learning on the academic achievement of BSED students?
3. Is there a significant relationship in the level of the effect of online learning when grouped according to student profile?
 - 3.1 Age
 - 3.2 Sex
 - 3.3 Year Level
4. What intervention program could be recommended based on the results?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study was a quantitative descriptive correlational research design. It identifies and describes how online learning influences the academic achievement of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students. The quantitative descriptive correlational design was appropriate as a means of identifying trends, relationships, and possible differences among variables without manipulating any aspect of the conditions of what the students experienced during their online learning course.

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Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were 30 BSED students who were part of the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) program at ACC during the 2024–2025 school year. Purposive sampling was used to obtain students who actively participated in online learning.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at ACC, situated in Abuyog, Leyte, Philippines. Specifically, among students enrolled in the Bachelor Education program. This institution was chosen due to its ongoing implementation of online learning modalities and accessibility to the researchers.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a structured questionnaire as the primary tool for collecting quantitative data. The instrument was divided into two parts: (i) Profile of the respondents this section collects basic demographic and contextual information about the respondents. (ii) Using Likert Scale to measure this section contains statements. The items are designed to assess the level of effect of online learning on academic achievement. They focus on comprehension of lessons, student motivation, academic performance, user-friendliness of platforms, and challenges related to internet connectivity.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the actual data collection, permission to distribute the questionnaire was sought from the college president. Researchers used a quantitative method to collect data. The survey questionnaire was a structured questionnaire that was used as a research instrument. Similarly, the instrument was validated by the experts to establish its content validity and operational suitability to the objectives of the study.

After validation, the revised questionnaire was distributed to the target respondents who met inclusion criteria that the researchers identified. Data were collected by administering and collecting the survey forms, and the responses were coded, tabulated, and statistically analyzed. The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were kept in the process.

Ethical Consideration

The researchers made sure that the participants signed informed consent before proceeding to answer the questionnaire. The anonymity of any response was kept and the respondents did not reveal any personal identifiers. It was voluntary, and respondents were free to withdraw any time during data collection. Confidentiality and anonymity were closely monitored, and all personal information were treated safely consistent with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 but exclusively used per academic research.

Method of Scoring and Interpretation

A 5-point Likert scale were used for the level of the effect of online learning on the academic achievement of BSED students

A. Likert Scale

- 5 – Strongly Agree
- 4 – Agree
- 3 - Neutral
- 2– Disagree
- 1– Strongly Disagree

B. Mean Scores Interpretation

Scale	Qualitative Description
4.20 – 5.00	Very High Effect
3.40 – 4.19	High Effect
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate Effect
1.80 – 2.59	Low Effect
1.0 – 1.79	Very Low Effect

C. Curriculum Interpretation Guide on Correlation (Pearson, 1895)

Range	Verbal Interpretation
± 1.00	Perfect Correlation
± 0.76 - ± 0.99	Very high positive/negative correlation
± 0.51 - ± 0.75	High positive/negative correlation
± 0.26 - ± 0.50	Moderately small positive/negative correlation
± 0.01 - ± 0.25	Very small positive/negative correlation
0.00	No correlation

Statistical Analysis

The collected profile data were tallied and analyzed using frequency count, percentage, weighted mean. To examine the relationships between the factors of online learning and the academic achievement of BSED students, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Age		
18-20	18	60
21-25	11	36.7
26-30	1	3.3
Total	30	100%
Sex		
Male	24	80
Female	6	20
Total	30	100%
Year Level		
1 st year	7	23.3
2 nd year	12	40
3 rd year	11	36.7
Total	30	100.0

Table 1

World Education Connect
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Age. The data in Table 1 revealed that the majority of BSED student respondents at ACC, comprising 60% (18 out of 30), were aged between 18 and 20 years old—typically first- or second-year college students. A significant portion, 36.7% (11 students), fall within the 21 to 25 age range, suggesting a mix of upperclassmen or those who may have experienced academic delays. Only one respondent (3.3%) is aged 26 to 30, indicating that older students are less represented in the study.

Sex. Majority of the BSED student respondents from ACC are female, making up 80% (24 out of 30) of the total participants. In contrast, only 20% (6 students) are male. This gender distribution suggests that the study's findings on the effects of online learning may reflect more strongly the experiences and perspectives of female students, who dominate the sample group.

Year level. Most of the BSED student respondents at ACC are in their 2nd year, accounting for 40% (12 out of 30), followed closely by 3rd-year students at 36.7% (11 respondents). First-year students make up the remaining 23.3% (7 respondents). This distribution suggests that the study primarily reflects the experiences of students who have already spent at least a year in college, offering insights into how online learning affects those with more academic exposure and possibly greater adaptability to virtual platforms.

Table 2. Weighted Mean on the level of the effect of online learning on the academic achievement of BSED students in terms of:

Academic Performance in Online Learning	MEAN	VI
My grades were lower in online learning compared to the face-to-face platform?	3.10	Moderate Effect
I perform better academically in online learning compared to face-to-face .	2.72	Moderate Effect
Online learning helps me understand lessons effectively.	2.72	Moderate Effect
I feel satisfied with my academic progress through online learning.	2.79	Moderate Effect
I complete academic tasks efficiently in an online setup.	3.62	High Effect
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.99	Moderate Effect
Access to Technology and Resources	MEAN	VI
I use a reliable device (laptop, tablet, or smartphone) for online learning.	4.03	High Effect
I have a stable internet connection for attending classes.	3.55	High Effect
I can easily access learning materials uploaded online.	3.79	High Effect
I rarely miss classes due to internet or device problems.	3.31	Moderate Effect
I complete academic tasks efficiently in an online setup.	3.59	High Effect
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.65	High Effect

Engagement and Motivation	MEAN	VI
I actively participate in online discussions and class activities.	3.34	Moderate Effect
I feel motivated to complete my online class assignments in an online setup.	3.38	Moderate Effect
Online learning keeps me focused and attentive during lessons.	2.83	Moderate Effect
I take initiative to learn even without being prompted by my instructor.	3.03	Moderate Effect
I remain interested and enthusiastic in online class topics.	3.21	Moderate Effect
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.16	Moderate Effect
Time Management and Self-Regulation	MEAN	VI
I am able to manage my time effectively for online schoolwork.	3.66	High Effect
I follow a consistent study routine at home.	3.55	High Effect
I complete tasks before deadlines without reminders.	3.59	High Effect
I am disciplined in balancing academic responsibilities and home duties.	3.59	High Effect
I avoid procrastinating when it comes to online schoolwork.	3.38	Moderate Effect
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.55	High Effect
Challenges Encountered in Online Learning	MEAN	VI
I often have problems with my internet connection during online classes.	3.86	High Effect
I find it difficult to concentrate during online lessons.	3.79	High Effect
Technical issues affect my ability to learn effectively	3.90	High Effect
I feel isolated and disconnected from classmates and instructors.	3.59	High Effect
Lack of physical classroom interaction affects my understanding of lessons.	3.72	High Effect
TOTAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.77	High Effect

Table 2 shows that the overall weighted mean of 2.99 suggested that BSED students at ACC perceive online learning to have a moderate impact on their academic performance. While many students felt they could complete tasks efficiently in an online setup (mean = 3.62, high effect), their responses showed mixed feelings about understanding lessons, performing better, and feeling satisfied with their progress and all rated with moderate effect. Notably, some students believed their grades were lower compared to face-to-face learning (mean = 3.10), hinting at challenges in adapting to the online environment.

The data also showed the overall weighted mean of 3.65 indicates that BSED students at ACC generally experience a high level of access to technology and resources in their online learning environment. Most respondents reported using reliable devices (mean = 4.03) and having stable

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internet connections (mean = 3.55), which are essential for attending classes and completing academic tasks efficiently (mean = 3.59). They also found it easy to access online learning materials (mean = 3.79). However, a slightly lower mean of 3.31 suggests that occasional issues with internet or devices still cause some students to miss classes.

On the other hand, it also indicated that BSED students at ACC perceived a moderate level of engagement and motivation in their online learning experience. While many students reported participating in discussions (mean = 3.34) and feeling motivated to complete assignments (mean = 3.38), others struggled with staying focused during lessons (mean = 2.83). The data suggests that although students are making efforts to stay involved and take initiative, maintaining consistent interest and attentiveness remains a challenge in the virtual setup.

Moreover, Table revealed that BSED students at ACC generally exhibit strong time management and self-regulation skills in an online learning environment. Most respondents reported being able to manage their time effectively (mean = 3.66), follow consistent study routines (mean = 3.55), and complete tasks before deadlines (mean = 3.59), showing a high level of personal discipline. Although avoiding procrastination scored slightly lower (mean = 3.38), it still reflects a moderate effect.

Finally, the overall weighted mean of 3.77 revealed that BSED students at ACC face significant challenges in online learning. Technical issues (mean = 3.90) and unstable internet connections (mean = 3.86) are the most pressing concerns, often disrupting their ability to learn effectively. Students also struggle with concentration (mean = 3.79) and feel the impact of reduced classroom interaction (mean = 3.72), which affects their understanding of lessons. Feelings of isolation (mean = 3.59) further highlight the emotional toll of remote learning.

Significant relationship between the level of the effect of online learning when grouped according to their profile

Correlations		
		LEVEL OF THE EFFECT OF ONLINE LEARNING
AGE	Pearson Correlation	.572
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001
	N	30
SEX	Pearson Correlation	-.174
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.376
	N	30
YEAR LEVEL	Pearson Correlation	.568
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002
	N	30

Based on the correlation analysis, there is a **high positive relationship** between both age ($r = .572$, $p = .001$) and year level ($r = .568$, $p = .002$) with the level of the effect of online learning on academic achievement among BSED students at ACC. These results suggest that older students and those in higher year levels tend to perceive online learning as more impactful, possibly due to their greater academic exposure and maturity. Meanwhile, **sex** shows a **very small negative correlation** ($r = -.174$, $p = .376$), which is not statistically significant. Given these findings, we **reject the null hypothesis (H_0)** and **accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a)**—indicating that students' profiles, particularly age and year level, significantly influence how online learning affects their academic achievement.

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What intervention program may be proposed to improve academic performance in online learning based on the findings?

Based on the findings, a well-rounded intervention program called "**CONNECT: Comprehensive Online Nurturing for engagement, Efficiency, and College Triumph**" may be proposed to support BSED students' academic performance in online learning. This program could include regular virtual mentoring sessions to boost motivation and engagement, structured time management workshops, and peer support groups to reduce feelings of isolation. It should also offer technical assistance and access to reliable devices and internet for students facing connectivity issues. By combining emotional support, academic guidance, and technological aid, CONNECT aims to create a more inclusive and empowering online learning environment where students feel equipped, connected, and confident to succeed.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, the study on the effect of online learning on the academic achievement of BSED students at ACC reveals a nuanced picture of both progress and struggle. While students generally show strength in time management, self-regulation, and access to technology, their academic performance, engagement, and motivation remain moderately affected. The challenges they face especially technical issues, poor concentration, and feelings of isolation, underscore the emotional and practical barriers that come with remote learning. Importantly, the data shows that age and year level significantly influence how students perceive the impact of online learning, suggesting that more mature and academically experienced students are better equipped to adapt. These insights highlight the need for targeted interventions that not only address technical gaps but also foster connection, motivation, and deeper learning engagement. By understanding students' lived experiences, educators and institutions can create more responsive and supportive online learning environments that truly empower students to succeed.

In light of the findings, it is recommended that ACC implement a student-centered support program that strengthens both the technical and emotional aspects of online learning. This includes providing reliable access to devices and internet connectivity, especially for those who struggle with frequent disruptions. Equally important is fostering a sense of connection and motivation through virtual peer mentoring, interactive learning strategies, and regular check-ins with instructors. Workshops on time management and self-discipline can further empower students to stay on track. By addressing the challenges and nurturing the strengths identified in the study, the college can create a more inclusive and effective online learning environment where every student feels supported and capable of succeeding.

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17383560

